

Strategy Document for Silicon Tracking and Vertexing for the EIC

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Introduction

As demonstrated in the EIC Yellow Report [1], the EIC will require a well-integrated, large acceptance tracking and vertexing system with high spatial resolution and low mass that exceeds the current capabilities of any existing highly granular pixel detectors. The only currently identified existing sensor technology that can meet these requirements in the timeframe available is Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (MAPS) in view of the particular requirements the EIC imposes on pixelation, power consumption, and material budget.

This document presents the strategy for the development of the EIC tracking and vertexing system based on a new generation MAPS in a commercial 65 nm CMOS imaging technology, with two fallback solutions based on MAPS sensors in 180 nm CMOS imaging technology. Both the main development path and the fallback solutions leverage on a collaboration with the ALICE experiment at CERN. The main axis is supposed to yield the detector matching the EIC requirements, whereas the fallback solutions are expected to result in some tradeoffs.

Constraints and Performance

In order for a strategy to be considered viable it must meet certain constraints. They include:

1. The product of the development plan must meet the requirements for the EIC tracking as laid out most recently in the EICUG Yellow Report.
2. The development plan must demonstrate that the technical objectives can credibly be met using the technology chosen.
3. The development plan must show that the full development plan can be achieved in the timeframe dictated by the project planning.

The presented plan for development of a 65 nm sensor and full tracking detector based on this sensor path meets these requirements.

The performance metric for the silicon tracking and vertexing is to fit into a suite of detectors that enable the physics measurements as established by the DOE call and the NAS report. This space has been explored in the EICUG Yellow Report (YR) and conclusions have been drawn about the required tracking and vertexing performance. This is captured in the YR tracking requirements table shown below.

Tracking requirements from PWGs							
			Momentum res.	Material budget	Minimum pT	Transverse pointing res.	
η							
-3.5 to -3.0	Central Detector	Backward Detector	$\sigma_{p/p} \sim 0.1\% \times p \oplus 0.5\%$	$\sim 5\% X_0$ or less	100-150 MeV/c		
-3.0 to -2.5					100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 40 \mu\text{m}$	
-2.5 to -2.0			$\sigma_{p/p} \sim 0.05\% \times p \oplus 0.5\%$		100-150 MeV/c		
-2.0 to -1.5			100-150 MeV/c		dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 20 \mu\text{m}$		
-1.5 to -1.0			100-150 MeV/c				
-1.0 to -0.5			100-150 MeV/c				
-0.5 to 0		Barrel	$\sigma_{p/p} \sim 0.05\% \times p \oplus 0.5\%$		100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 20/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 5 \mu\text{m}$	
0 to 0.5							
0.5 to 1.0		Forward Detector	$\sigma_{p/p} \sim 0.05\% \times p \oplus 1\%$		100-150 MeV/c		
1.0 to 1.5					100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 20 \mu\text{m}$	
1.5 to 2.0					100-150 MeV/c		
2.0 to 2.5					100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 40 \mu\text{m}$	
2.5 to 3.0					$\sigma_{p/p} \sim 0.1\% \times p \oplus 2\%$	100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 60 \mu\text{m}$
3.0 to 3.5					100-150 MeV/c	dca(xy) $\sim 30/pT \mu\text{m} \oplus 60 \mu\text{m}$	

Figure 1: Requirements Table

The YR simulations indicate the need for a spatial resolution of 5 μm or better in tracking layers and disks, and around 3 μm in the vertex layers, combined with a material budget $\leq 0.1\% X/X_0$ in the vertex layers, $\leq 0.3\% X/X_0$ in the tracking layers and disks. In addition to these requirements, an EIC silicon tracking detector needs to be designed with an integration time below 2 μs to cope with the interaction frequency expected at the highest luminosity, i.e. 500 kHz at $10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$.

Planning and Schedule

As a project schedule has been established, any silicon-based detector candidate (including sensors, mechanics, cooling, powering, RDO, etc.) that is a prospective solution must be able to show a credible path to meeting the project schedule need by project CD-3 and be ready in a full working form by EIC CD-4a.

The schedule for the proposed detector R&D leading up to CD-3 in Q2 2024 has been presented by the “eRD25: Silicon Tracking and Vertexing Consortium” at the EIC Generic Detector R&D meeting in March 2020 [2]. This schedule is based on the proposed strategy and meets the projected EIC installation timeline.

Beyond CD3, the schedule towards CD4 can be estimated by looking at the most recent project of similar magnitude (10 m^2): the ALICE ITS upgrade, currently the largest MAPS detector ever built. The construction phase of this project took 2.5 years and required 11 dedicated assembly sites worldwide. A similar number of years was needed for the development of the necessary tooling, assembly procedures and infrastructure. Any credible proposed effort will require a broad base or the capability of developing a broad base of participating institutions.

Current Status and Strategy

The technology identified to satisfy the tracking requirements captured in figure 1 is MAPS. None of the existing production version or prototype MAPS sensors meet the requirements as set out in the Yellow Report. It is thus necessary that the EIC community develops a sensor and the detector infrastructure that can meet these stringent requirements.

The strategy identified to reach this goal is to partner with the ALICE ITS3 project to develop a new generation MAPS sensor in a commercial 65 nm CMOS technology, with two fallback solutions for the sensor development that is the most risky, lengthy and expensive item of development. A full description of the planned development can be found in the eRD25 proposal [3]. Leveraging the ongoing R&D for the ALICE ITS3, a full detector infrastructure will be developed in parallel with the sensor to implement the EIC tracking and vertexing system.

This strategy is based on the following reasons:

- The specified ALICE ITS3 65 nm MAPS sensor has performance that meets or even exceeds the EIC tracking and vertexing requirements as demonstrated in simulations presented in the Yellow Report and in the eRD25 proposal and report [2, 3].
- The development of the EIC tracking and vertexing system can leverage on a well-funded, large effort at CERN, open to non-ALICE members to contribute to the R&D to develop and use the technology for other applications.
- The ALICE ITS3 approach to develop an ultra-low mass vertex detector is particularly attractive for the EIC vertex layers that could be easily designed with the same technologies developed for the ITS3 detector.
- The schedule of the ITS3 and EIC projects are well aligned.
- The ITS3 project has a 180 nm MAPS sensor fallback solution in case the main 65 nm development would not prove feasible on the required time scale. The decision will be taken later this year after results from the first submission in 65 nm.
- A large group of EIC institutes have expressed interest in this proposed development and joined to form the EIC Silicon Consortium [5], providing the required broad base of expertise for the full detector implementation. Some of these institutes are already working with ITS3 on sensor development [2].

Should the timeline of development of a sensor in either 65 or 180 nm CMOS imaging technology with ITS3 encounter delays that would comprise the successful start of the EIC physics programme as planned, a further fall back solution would be to use the ALPIDE sensor currently installed in the ALICE inner tracker, and upgrade to the new sensor later in the EIC experiments lifetime. While it is clear that ALPIDE does not meet the requirements identified in the Yellow Report, in this scenario, ALPIDE is identified to be the only existing sensor option ready to be deployed to allow the EIC detector to have some vertex and tracking capability from day one. Resources would need to be dedicated to evaluating the detailed impact on physics performance before ALPIDE can be considered as a possibly viable but certainly suboptimal fallback option.

Sensor Development Considerations and Flow

Three technology options are currently foreseen for silicon detectors at the EIC: a new generation MAPS sensor in 65 nm CMOS imaging technology (main development path); a new MAPS sensor in 180 nm CMOS imaging technology (fallback option 1); the ALICE ITS ALPIDE sensor (fallback option 2). Both the main development path and the fallback option 1 will be carried out in collaboration with the ALICE ITS3 project.

These options come with different levels of performance and development risks. All three options also involve engagement with other groups, namely with the ALICE collaboration at CERN, and therefore each

option also has various requirements regarding the formalization of engagement with these groups. Furthermore, the EIC is likely to require detectors beyond what will be developed in these common developments. Moving from the shared developments to an EIC detector will require legal agreement on access and also a decision on when to branch from the common sensor.

All MAPS sensor developments require legal agreements in areas such as Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs), agreements on the sharing of design databases, or agreements on silicon supply. Whilst the members of the EIC Silicon Consortium have considerable experience in MAPS design and in handling these issues, the EIC project and most of the EICSC institutions presently do not have this legal access in place for the options discussed here. It should be further noted that these legal points, as well as the silicon development risks discussed elsewhere in this document apply equally to all silicon development projects.

The table below captures the performance, legal requirements and risks of the three options considered in this document. Performance of the 65nm chip and ALPIDE are taken from https://indico.cern.ch/event/813597/contributions/3727803/attachments/1989307/3315951/2020-02-18_Trento2020_ITS3.pdf. Performance for the new 180 nm sensor are estimated based on studies by eRD18, a summary of which can be found at <https://wiki.bnl.gov/conferences/images/6/65/ERD18ReportJan20v0.1.pdf>

Specification	Unit	Technology Option		
		65nm (jointly with ITS3)	180nm (jointly with ITS3)	ALPIDE
Pixel Pitch	µm	10	20-25	27 x 29
Chip Dimensions	mm ²	?	?	15x30
Silicon Thickness	µm	50	50	50-100
Timing Resolution	ns	<100 (option to <10)	<100n (option to <20)	>1000
Power Density	mW/cm ²	20	40-50	20-40
NIEL	1MeV neq/cm ²	UNKNOWN	3e13	3e13
TID	MRad	UNKNOWN	3	3
Fake Hit Rate	Events/pixel	<10e-7	<10e-7	<10e-7
Organisational/Legal Issues		1. Relies on engagement with the CERN ITS3 development. Currently being carried on informally. Reliance on this for full detector development would require a more formal relationship.	1. Relies on engagement with the CERN ITS3 development. Currently being carried on informally. Reliance on this for full detector development would require a more formal relationship.	1. Would require access to ALPIDE chips. This will require either a supply agreement with CERN or alternatively, CERN's

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. NDAs for TJ65 nm is needed to be established by CERN and signed by the participating institutions. 3. Design sharing agreements are needed for all participating institutes. 4. Note that as the EIC requires staves as well as bent chips, access to design databases is needed, <i>not just manufactured silicon</i>. This will require multiple legal agreements. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. NDAs for TJ180 need to be signed 3. Design sharing agreements are needed for all participating institutes. 4. Note that as the EIC requires staves as well as bent chips, access to design databases is needed, <i>not just manufactured silicon</i>. This will require multiple legal agreements. 	<p>agreement to share the database for further manufacture .</p>
Risks		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential issues with the process – e.g. radiation hardness, 2. Design feasibility – e.g. achievable compactness of the pixel design and resulting power density. 3. Potential need of several design/fabrication iterations due to chip bugs. 4. CERN may not wish to share chips/design databases. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential need of several design/fabrication iterations due to chip bugs. 2. CERN may not wish to share chips/design databases. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CERN may not wish to share chips/design databases.
Notes		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Achieving targeted smallest pixel size 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sensor performance at 	

		only possible with 65nm process	least the same as ALPIDE or better depending on whether the same process is used, or its modified version for full depletion 2. Performance estimates based on studies from eRD18	
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The intense relationships between these options can be summarized in a flowchart as shown below. This shows how the 1st choice 65nm development is likely to proceed, how it might move to fallback options at more well-known processes and where the EIC might branch from these developments. It also shows the points at which formal legal arrangements need to be in place to allow work to continue. Note that the points at which legal agreements are shown in the flowchart are the **latest possible point at which they will be needed**. It is advisable to have prepared these well before they are required – for example, if an ALPIDE fallback is needed, it would cause serious delay to the project if it were only discovered at that point that an agreement could not be reached.

The foreseen ITS3 schedule is taken from

https://indico.desy.de/event/24227/contributions/53047/attachments/65072/80293/2021-04-07_Terascale_ITS3.pdf.

EIC Silicon Acquisition Strategy

Adaptation and acquisition plan

The project relies on:

- 1) The extension of sensor and detector technologies being developed by the ALICE collaboration at CERN, including reusing their expertise and, if applicable, building upon the parts from the existing designs. The ALICE ITS-3 sensor project was set up from the beginning to welcome outside institutions and consortiums as collaborators in the chip design and to make agreements to share the IP that is to come from this effort.
- 2) The expertise and capabilities of the NP community to develop the identified detector solutions for the specific application at the EIC.
- 3) The overall expertise of the consortium members in developing pixel detectors for applications in Photon-Science and High energy Physics.

Conclusion

This document presents a strategy for the development of an EIC tracking and vertexing system based on synergies with ALICE experiment tracking technologies, both present and future ones, to develop the required sensor and detector infrastructure. The synergies of joining the ALICE effort are very high and provide a large multi-institutional collaborative platform with excellent prospects for success in the sensor and infrastructure realm. The sensor development plan is solid with a main path forward that would give the best physics performance, a first fallback solution that would still meet the requirements, and a second fallback solution that would allow the EIC experiment to start on time albeit with a compromised physics performance to be quantified. Since the paths explored here all lead through the ALICE/CERN developments, it would be prudent to begin discussions with ALICE/CERN management exploring the use of the technology.

References

- [1] EIC Yellow Report, http://www.eicug.org/web/sites/default/files/Yellow_Report_v1.1.pdf
- [2] eRD25 progress report, <https://wiki.bnl.gov/conferences/images/3/36/ERD25-Mar20-final.pdf>, March 2021
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- [4] Electron-Ion Collider Detector Requirements and R&D Handbook, http://eicug.org/web/sites/default/files/EIC_HANDBOOK_v1.2.pdf, version 1.2, February 2020
- [5] EIC SC Expression of Interest, <https://indico.bnl.gov/event/8552/contributions/43219/>, November 2020